

1,3-Dipolar Character of 6-Membered Aromatic Rings. Part XXXVII†. Mass Spectrometry of Diazinium Betaines

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Diazinium betaines evaporate as mesoions rather than undergoing valence tautomerism. The fragmentation patterns are elucidated by metastable peaks and precise mass measurements and discussed.

1-ALKYL-3-OXIDOPYRIDINIUMS (1) are evaporated without prior skeletal rearrangement in the mass spectrometer². Undheim and Hansen³ have demonstrated by comparison of the ionization potentials of 2-benzyl-4-oxidoisoquinolinium (3) with its valence isomer (4) that 3 evaporates as a mesoion rather than undergoing valence isomerism. We have recently provided further support to this hypothesis⁴ in the case of 3-oxido-1-phenylpyridinium (2) by comparison of the high resolution mass spectra of (2) and its valence isomeric cyclopentenone (5). We now describe the fragmentation of a number of diazinium betaines.

3-Methyl-1-oxidophthalazintium (6)

The diazinium betaine (6) gives the molecular ion as the base peak. The appearance of the molecular ion as a base peak is characteristic of five-membered mesoionic compounds⁵ and six-membered azinium betaines^{6,6}. The fragmentation (Scheme 1) of 6 initially

follows the pattern discovered for 1-aryl-3-oxidopyridinium betaines^{4,6}. The molecular ion fragments mainly by CO expulsion and the corresponding metastable peak is found. The indazole species ($a \leftrightarrow b$) thus produced readily loses a hydrogen radical to realise the energetically favoured protonated cinnolinium ion e , m/e 131. C-Alkyl aromatic and heteroaromatic compounds⁷ readily undergo loss of hydrogen radical followed by ring expansion e.g. N-methylpyrrole⁸. However such ring expansions are practically absent with N-alkyl dinitrogen aromatic compounds.

The indazole species further fragments to species c and d . The cinnolinium species e so produced fragments further by loss of HCN to f . The fragmentation pattern of phthalazin-1(2H)-one (7) is similar to that of the betaine 6 (Table) although the intensity of the M-28 ion is very small. Bowie *et al.*⁹ and Zyakun *et al.*¹⁰ showed by high resolution mass spectrometry, that this loss of 28 mass units is due to CO.

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Scheme 1

2-Methylphthalazin-1-one (8) (Table) loses CO exclusively to yield the base peak at M-28 and no M-29 is found. 1-Methoxyphthalazine (9) (Table) fragments to give M-1 (67%), M-28 (15%), M-29 (47%), M-30 (27%) and M-31 (25%) ions. The presence of an M-1 ion is characteristic for heterocycles possessing amino, methyl, phenyl or methoxy substituents adjacent to the ring nitrogen⁹. The base peak of compound 9 is at *m/e* 103.

It is evident from the Table that all four compounds 6-9 have distinct fragmentation patterns. Thus the betaine does not undergo *trans* alkylation⁹ prior to

evaporation. The foregoing results do not exclude evaporation of the betaine as its valence tautomer 10; however, by analogy with 2-benzyl-4-oxidoisoquinolinium⁹, betaine 6 probably volatilises as the mesoion.

1-Methyl- and 1,6-dimethyl-3-oxidopyridazinium (11 and 12)

The corresponding molecular ion is the base peak for each of the betaines 11 and 12. The fragmentation

pattern (Scheme 2) is similar to that for 3-methyl-1-oxidophthalazinium (6): expulsion of CO leads to a radical ion [*g* ↔ *h*] which fragments to give *i* and *j*, or loses H• to ion *k*. Further loss of HCN from *k* yields the protonated species, 1. Again by analogy with N-benzyl-4-oxidoisoquinolinium, it is assumed that the betaines 11 and 12 evaporate as such and not as the valence isomers 13 and 14. Pyridazin-3-one (15) and 6-methylpyridazin-3-one (16) also both fragment specifically by the initial loss of carbon monoxide⁹.

1-Oxido-3-phenylphthalazinium (17)

The phthalazinium betaine 17 yields the molecular ion as the base peak. The molecular ion fragments by CO expulsion. The indazole species [*m* ↔ *n*] then loses (Scheme 3) C₆H₅N₂⁺ to give *o*, or splits off C₇H₅N₂⁺ to give the phenyl ion *p*, or C₇H₅N₂ to the phenyl ion radical *q*.

6-Chloro-2-methyl-4-oxidoindolinium (18)

The molecular ion (base peak) fragments initially by expulsion of CO (Table-1) (metastable peak). The chloroindazole species [*r* ↔ *s*] readily loses a hydrogen

TABLE 1—RELATIVE INTENSITIES OF THE MAJOR IONS IN THE MASS SPECTRA

6 m/e	161	160	133	132	131	104	103	90	89	82	81	64	63	62	51	50	43	42	39									
% I	11	100	7	38	18	16	8	12	35	9	10	23	14	8	11	16	13	16										
7 m/e	147	146	128	118	91	90	89	63	50																			
% I	7	100	8	18	10	14	37	15	9																			
8 m/e	161	160	132	105	104	103	89	76	63																			
% I	8	80	100	6	28	8	46	10	17																			
9 m/e	161	160	159	132	131	130	129	104	103	102	89	76	63															
% I	7	80	67	15	47	27	25	15	100	9	33	5	6															
11 m/e	110	82	81	66	55	54	53	52	43	42	41	40	39															
% I	100	50	27	5	7	12	5	6	22	4	7	10	74															
12 m/e	124	96	95	81	68	67	66	56	55	54	53	52	51	50	43													
% I	100	55	40	10	9	5	6	15	10	14	57	15	20	14	35													
17 m/e	223	222	221	194	193	165	130	91	89	77	76	63	51															
% I	18	100	66	11	9	12	9	19	17	35	8	13	22															
18 m/e	196	194	168	167	166	165	140	139	138	127	126	125	124	113	112	111	110	97	98	97	90	75	74	73	64	63	62	61
% I	37	100	15	11	44	18	4	4	9	4	11	17	11	2	4	3	2	6	6	9	6	7	4	6	4	9	7	4

SCHEME 2

SCHEME 3

SCHEME 4

atom to form the protonated chlorocinnolinium ion *t*, *m/e* 165 (167) (Scheme 4). Subsequent expulsion of HCN yields the species, *u*.

Experimental

Low resolution mass spectra were recorded on a Hitachi-Perkin-Elmer RMU-6E mass spectrometer. Compounds were introduced via the heated direct insertion probe. The source temperature was kept at 300 °C and the electron energy at 50 and 70 eV.

The high resolution mass spectra were recorded on an A. E. I. MS-9 mass spectrometer coupled to an IBM 1130 computer. All compounds were introduced via the heated direct insertion probe. The source temperature was kept at 200 °C and the electron energy and trap current at 70 eV and 500 μA, respectively. Precise masses were obtained by peak matching at a resolving power of *ca.* 10,000 (10% valley definition).

Syntheses

3-Methyl-1-oxidophthalazinium,^{11,12} 1-oxido-3-phenylphthalazinium,¹³ 1-methyl-3-oxidopyridazinium,¹² 1,6-dimethyl-3-oxidopyridazinium,¹² phthalazin-1(2H)one,¹⁴ 6-chloro-2-methyl-4-oxidocinnolinium,¹² 2-methylphthalazin-1-one,¹⁵ 1-methoxyphthalazine¹⁶ were prepared according to the literature.

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